

Mapping Riparian and Wetland Weeds with High Resolution Satellite Imagery

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ABSTRACT

QuickBird multi-spectral satellite imagery was evaluated for detecting weeds in waterways and wetlands in Texas. Plant species studied included giant reed (*Arundo donax* L.), waterhyacinth [*Eichhornia crassipes* (Mart.) Solms], and giant salvinia (*Salvinia molesta* Mitchell). Accuracy assessment results performed on the unsupervised classified maps for each species were: giant reed, 94.4% producer's accuracy and 100% user's accuracy; waterhyacinth, 100% producer's accuracy and 80% user's accuracy; and giant salvinia, 93.9% producer's accuracy and 92% user's accuracy. These results indicate that QuickBird imagery can be used successfully to map infestations of these three weeds.

Introduction

The use of remote sensing for wetland assessment is well established. Landsat and SPOT satellite imagery have been used to differentiate among wetland plant communities and species (Carter 1982). In the past few years, high spatial resolution (2.4 to 4 m) satellite imagery

from commercial companies has become available for remote sensing applications. The IKONOS and QuickBird satellites enable observations in visible and near-infrared wavebands. IKONOS data has been used successfully to classify wetland habitats (Dechka et al. 2002) and QuickBird imagery has proven useful for mapping rangeland and riparian cover types (Everitt et al. 2005).

In this paper the authors present an overview of their own research using QuickBird imagery coupled with image analysis techniques for detecting and mapping invasive weeds in waterways and riparian zones.

General Procedures

With the exception of giant salvinia, data presented in this paper have been previously published.. Multi-spectral satellite imagery from the DigitalGlobe, Inc., (Longmont, Colorado) QuickBird high resolution satellite was used for the these studies. The imagery has a spatial resolution of 2.4 m. The green (520 to 600-nm), red (630 to 690-nm), and near-infrared (760 to

900-nm) bands were used in the studies presented here. Procedures used for image processing and analysis, as well as other detailed information on the studies presented here can be obtained from the literature citations. Accuracy assessments were conducted to verify image classification maps. The overall accuracy, producer's accuracy, user's accuracy, and overall kappa coefficient were calculated for each site (Congalton and Green 1999).

Results and Discussion

Giant reed

Giant reed is a weedy perennial grass 3 to 10 m tall growing in many-stemmed cane-like clumps. Giant reed is believed to be native to the Old World from Spain to India, but has been widely introduced as an ornamental and for bank stabilization (Polunin and Huxley 1987). Giant reed was introduced to California from the Mediterranean in the 1820's and quickly became naturalized (Horshovsky 1987). It now occurs throughout the southern United States from Maryland to California, but is most invasive along creeks and rivers in the southwestern United States.

Everitt et al. (2005) used QuickBird satellite imagery to distinguish and map giant reed infestations along the Rio Grande in southwest Texas. Figure 1A shows a subset false color QuickBird image of the giant reed study site on the Rio Grande. The arrow on the image points to the dark pink tonal response of giant reed that can be easily distinguished from the other surface types. Mixed brush has a dark red to reddish-brown response, dry grass/scrub brush has a variable blue-gray to gray color, and soil has a white to white-gray tone. The Rio Grande (dark blue) borders the lower portion of the image.

Figure 1. QuickBird false color satellite image (A) obtained September 15, 2003 of the giant reed study site on the Rio Grande near Del Rio, Texas. The arrow on the print points to the dark pink image response of giant reed. Unsupervised classification (B) of the satellite image. Color codes for the various surface types are: yellow = giant reed, red = mixed brush, green = dry grass/scrub brush, white = soil, and blue = water.

Figure 1B shows the unsupervised computer classification of the satellite image (Fig. 1A). The classification had an overall accuracy of 83%. Giant reed had a producer's accuracy of 94.4% and a user's accuracy of 100%. Thomlinson et al. (1999) set a target of an overall accuracy of 85% with no class less than 70%. Based on these guidelines the overall accuracy was adequate, while the producer's and user's accuracies of giant reed were excellent. The kappa estimate was 0.770, indicating the classification achieved an accuracy that is 77% better than would be expected from the random assignment of pixels to classes.

Waterhyacinth

Waterhyacinth is a floating, aquatic macrophyte that often invades and clogs waterways. Native to South America, this

weed continues to afflict and dominate the fresh water bodies and waterways in more than 50 countries. Waterhyacinth is believed to have been introduced into the United States in the mid 1880's in Louisiana (Tabita and Woods 1962). It is now found from Virginia to Florida and west to Texas and Missouri; it also occurs in California (Correll and Correll 1972).

Figure 2. QuickBird false color satellite image (A) obtained May 17, 2005 of the waterhyacinth study site on Lake Corpus Christi near Mathis, Texas. The arrow on the print points to the bright red image tonal response of waterhyacinth. Unsupervised classification (B) of the satellite image. Color codes for the various cover types are: light green = waterhyacinth, dark green = mixed vegetation, purple = weed stubble, and blue = water.

Everitt and Yang (2007) recently completed a study using QuickBird imagery to distinguish and map waterhyacinth on a south Texas reservoir. The false color subset QuickBird image of the study area is shown in Figure 2A. Waterhyacinth has a bright red image response and occurs at several locations in the scene. Mixed vegetation has variable gray, grayish-red, and red to dull red tones and occurs along the left side and upper portions of the scene. Weed stubble (upper center) has a dark brown to nearly black tone, while water has a light blue to whitish-blue response.

The unsupervised classification of the false color satellite image (Fig. 2A) of the study area is shown in Figure 2B. The

overall classification accuracy was 90%. Waterhyacinth had a producer's accuracy of 100% and a user's accuracy of 80%. The kappa estimate was 0.862.

Giant salvinia

Giant salvinia is a floating aquatic fern native to Brazil that has spread to many other freshwaters of the world (Oliver 1993). Giant salvinia damages ecosystems by overgrowing and replacing native plants that provide food and habitat for wildlife. This weed has been reported from all of the coastal southern United States from Texas to Virginia, as well as California, Arizona, and Hawaii (USGS 2004).

A study was recently initiated to determine the feasibility of using false color QuickBird imagery to distinguish infestations of giant salvinia in east Texas on Toledo Bend Reservoir near Huxley. On the satellite image mature giant salvinia populations had a whitish-pink image tone, while less dense, immature populations had a blue-pink image tone (image not shown). Mixed woody vegetation had a dark red to reddish-brown response, mixed aquatic vegetation had variable lighter red to reddish-pink tones, and water had a dark blue to black color.

The overall accuracy of the unsupervised classification of the QuickBird image was 92.9%. Giant salvinia had a producer's accuracy of 93.9% and a user's accuracy of 92%, both considered excellent. The kappa estimate was 0.899.

Conclusions

Our results indicate that QuickBird satellite imagery combined with image analysis can be a useful tool for distinguishing and mapping invasive weeds in waterways and wetlands. The satellite

imagery can measure the entire spatial extent of an area and serve as a permanent geographically located image database to monitor future contraction or spread of weed populations over time.

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